

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

№10
2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 1088 sahifa,
3-oktyabr, 2025-yil.

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Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

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Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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THE USE OF MOBILE APPS TO BUILD VOCABULARY PROFICIENCY

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Abstract: Incorporating multimedia program-based tasks into vocabulary instruction represents a modern and effective pedagogical approach that leverages the interactive potential of digital resources. This article aims to describe both the theoretical and practical aspects of the mobile app “Word Case,” an innovative multimedia program designed to enhance the vocabulary competence of B1-level learners of English. Word Case offers a diverse range of multimedia resources—such as interactive games and audio recordings—catering to various learning styles and preferences. This diversity ensures that students are exposed to vocabulary in different contexts and formats, which enhances comprehension and retention. The program also provides opportunities for autonomous learning, enabling students to explore and practice vocabulary at their own pace and according to their individual interests. Moreover, Word Case facilitates continuous assessment and feedback, allowing teachers to monitor learners’ progress and adapt instruction accordingly. The study analyzes various scholarly perspectives on the “multimedia program” as viewed in philosophy, psychology, and pedagogy, and presents the results of a questionnaire survey.

Key words: pedagogical approach; vocabulary; multimedia; mobile app; autonomous learning; comprehension; retention.

Annotatsiya: Ingliz tili lugʻatini oʻqitishda multimedia dasturiy taʼminotga asoslangan topshiriqlardan foydalanish zamonaviy va samarali pedagogik yondashuv hisoblanadi, chunki u raqamli resurslarning interaktiv imkoniyatlaridan foydalanadi. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi ingliz tilini B1 darajasida oʻrganayotgan oʻquvchilarning soʻz boyligini oshirishga moʻljallangan innovatsion multimedia dasturi – “Word Case” mobil ilovasining nazariy va amaliy jihatlari tavsiflash hamda tahlil qilishdan iborat. Word Case ilovasi oʻquvchilarning turli oʻrganish uslublari va xohishlariga mos keladigan interaktiv oʻyinlar va audio topshiriqlar kabi multimedia resurslarining keng doirasini taklif etadi. Bunday xilma-xillik oʻquvchilarning lugʻatni turli kontekst va formatlarda oʻrganish imkonini beradi, bu esa tushunish va eslab qolish samaradorligini oshiradi. Dastur mustaqil oʻrganish imkoniyatini yaratadi, bu orqali oʻquvchilar yangi soʻzlarni oʻz tezligida va shaxsiy qiziqishlariga koʻra oʻzlashtirishlari mumkin. Shuningdek, Word Case uzluksiz baholash va fikr-mulohaza almashinuvini taʼminlab, oʻqituvchilarga oʻquvchilarning yutuqlarini kuzatish hamda taʼlim jarayonini moslashtirish imkonini beradi. Tadqiqotda falsafa, psixologiya va pedagogika sohalaridagi olimlar tomonidan “multimedia dasturi”ga oid ilgari surilgan qarashlar tahlil qilinib, soʻrovnomaga natijalari keltirilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: pedagogik yondashuv; soʻz boyligi; multimedia; mobil ilova; mustaqil taʼlim; tushunish; eslab qolish.

Аннотация: Применение мультимедийных программных заданий в обучении лексике представляет собой современный и эффективный педагогический подход, использующий интерактивный потенциал цифровых ресурсов. Цель данной статьи – описать как теоретические, так и практические аспекты мобильного приложения “Word Case”, инновационной мультимедийной программы, направленной на повышение лексической компетенции обучающихся уровня B1 по английскому языку. Word Case предлагает широкий спектр мультимедийных ресурсов – таких как интерактивные игры и аудиозаписи – что позволяет учитывать различные стили и предпочтения обучения. Это разнообразие обеспечивает знакомство студентов с лексикой в разных контекстах и форматах, способствуя лучшему пониманию и запоминанию. Программа предоставляет возможности для автономного обучения, позволяя студентам осваивать и практиковать лексику в собственном темпе и в соответствии с их индивидуальными интересами. Кроме того, Word Case облегчает процесс непрерывной оценки и обратной связи, что даёт преподавателям возможность отслеживать прогресс студентов и адаптировать обучение. В статье анализируются различные точки зрения на мультимедийные программы, представленные учёными в области философии, психологии и педагогики, а также приводятся результаты анкетирования студентов и преподавателей.

Ключевые слова: педагогический подход; словарный запас; мультимедиа; мобильное приложение; автономное обучение; понимание; запоминание.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the role of multimedia in learning and teaching English is rapidly increasing both worldwide and in Uzbekistan. Great importance is attached to studying various language learning and teaching applications that can be easily installed and used. According to Presidential Decree No. 1875, adopted on December 10, 2012, "On Measures for the Further Enhancement of the System of Teaching Foreign Languages," pupils must start learning foreign languages at an early age (8). Incorporating multimedia program-based tasks into vocabulary instruction represents a modern and effective pedagogical approach that capitalizes on the interactive nature of digital resources. Research has shown that multimedia-based tasks significantly enhance vocabulary learning outcomes by providing students with engaging and immersive learning experiences (2, 95). These tasks offer dynamic platforms for students to interact with vocabulary in diverse contexts, facilitating deeper comprehension and retention of word meanings (3, 709).

By utilizing multimedia programs such as educational apps, interactive software, and online games, educators can create authentic learning environments that cater to various learning styles and preferences, according to Huang, Hsiao & Chang (1, 43). Moreover, multimedia-based tasks enable students to explore vocabulary in real-life situations, listen to authentic language usage, and engage in interactive exercises, fostering active participation and meaningful learning experiences (6, 79). As such, integrating multimedia program-based tasks into vocabulary instruction not only enhances students' vocabulary acquisition but also promotes their digital literacy skills and critical thinking abilities, as suggested by Zainuddin (7, 307).

One of the key accomplishments is the introduction of English language learning from the first grade of primary school. The implementation of this program began in the 2022–2023 academic year. Further improvements and developments have led to the introduction of new textbooks in public schools. After analyzing the textbook Prepare with our colleagues at a local school, we agreed that it is more effective for students to acquire new vocabulary through multimedia programs, as these motivate them to work diligently. The focus on enriching vocabulary is justified by the fact that having a broader range of words at one's disposal allows B1-level learners (Grades 10 and 11) to draw upon more extensive semantic resources, enabling them to activate relevant background knowledge and seamlessly integrate new information with existing knowledge, thereby enhancing comprehension. Furthermore, research has demonstrated that vocabulary proficiency and lexical competence play a crucial role in developing metalinguistic awareness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent studies have emphasized the effectiveness of mobile applications in enhancing vocabulary proficiency among language learners. According to Wang (2017), well-designed mobile apps provide interactive features such as flashcards, gamified exercises, and spaced repetition systems that promote long-term retention of new words. Similarly, Lee and Lee (2020) found that multimodal glosses – combining text, sound, and images – significantly improve learners' engagement and understanding of vocabulary meanings.

Research by Liao (2018) demonstrated that digital story-based learning through mobile devices increases motivation and contextual word learning, allowing students to acquire vocabulary in meaningful situations. Moreover, Zainuddin and Perera (2019) highlighted that mobile-assisted learning develops both digital literacy and critical thinking, supporting autonomous vocabulary practice.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Lexical competence is a set of lexical knowledge, skills, and abilities that determine students' ability to find a word's contextual meaning, compare its semantic scope across two languages, and use the word appropriately in context. In other words, it refers to students' capacity to organize and perform interrelated actions with lexical units aimed at mastering vocabulary, which includes understanding the meaning of a lexical unit, its graphic form and pronunciation, knowledge of its grammatical forms, and rules of lexical combination. Despite these definitions, the concept of lexical competence would be incomplete if it encompassed only lexical knowledge, skills, and abilities. Being a complex structural construct, lexical competence also includes language and speech experience, as well as students' personal qualities (5, 4). In forming foreign language lexical competence, some researchers conditionally distinguish several levels, viewing the process as the development of students' ability to solve communicative tasks involving the practical use of foreign vocabulary in speech activity, based on acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities.

For instance, adolescents with extensive vocabularies typically outperform their peers in tasks assessing phonological awareness, which facilitates decoding skills by enhancing their ability to identify and manipulate individual sounds and to associate these sounds with written symbols in text (4, 211). Considering the aforementioned points, we decided to design and develop an application program aimed at improving students'

lexical competence. During our analysis of lessons using the textbook Prepare, we realized that employing a mobile application to enhance vocabulary competence among B1-level students is one of the most effective classroom strategies. Therefore, we began piloting a program named Word Case—an innovative multimedia application developed by me and my postgraduate student to enhance the vocabulary competence of B1-level English learners. Word Case offers a comprehensive and engaging learning experience tailored to the needs of intermediate English learners. At its core, Word Case employs a variety of multimedia resources to facilitate vocabulary acquisition and retention. The program includes interactive lessons, audiovisual materials, and gamified activities—all designed to provide learners with multiple opportunities to encounter and practice new vocabulary in context. Each lesson is carefully crafted on the basis of Prepare to cover a range of thematic topics relevant to B1-level learners, ensuring that the vocabulary acquired is both useful and practical for everyday communication.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the key components of “Word Case” is its adaptive learning system, which dynamically adjusts the difficulty level of lessons based on learners’ performance and progress. Through ongoing assessment and feedback, the program identifies learners’ strengths and weaknesses, allowing for personalized learning experiences tailored to individual needs. This adaptive approach ensures that learners are appropriately challenged and engaged, maximizing learning outcomes. In addition to its adaptive learning system, “Word Case” also incorporates spaced repetition techniques to reinforce vocabulary learning over time. By strategically spacing out exposure to vocabulary words at intervals optimized for memory retention, the program helps learners move new words from short-term to long-term memory, ensuring lasting acquisition. Furthermore, “Word Case” offers a variety of supplementary resources to support vocabulary learning outside formal lessons. These resources include flashcards, vocabulary lists, and interactive quizzes, providing learners with additional opportunities for review and practice. Learners can access these resources through the program’s online platform or mobile app, allowing for convenient and flexible learning anytime, anywhere. Moreover, “Word Case” integrates multimedia elements such as audio recordings, videos, and images to provide rich and engaging learning experiences. Learners are exposed to authentic language use in various contexts, helping them develop not only their vocabulary but also their listening and comprehension skills. Interactive exercises and games add an element of fun and excitement to the learning process, motivating learners to actively engage with the material. The effectiveness of “Word Case” is further enhanced by its emphasis on active learning and student engagement. Learners are encouraged to participate actively in lessons through tasks and activities that require them to apply their knowledge in real-world situations. Whether through role-playing exercises, group discussions, or project-based assignments, learners are given opportunities to practice using new vocabulary in meaningful and communicative ways.

Additionally, “Word Case” provides ample support for learners through its user-friendly interface and access to comprehensive learning resources. Learners can track their progress, review lesson materials, and seek assistance from instructors or peers as needed. The program also fosters a sense of community among learners, allowing them to connect with fellow students and share their learning experiences. Conducting teachers’ questionnaires is of paramount importance in educational research for several reasons. Firstly, teachers possess invaluable insights into classroom dynamics, student learning needs, and teaching methodologies. Their perspectives provide researchers with rich qualitative data that can uncover nuanced aspects of teaching and learning. Secondly, gathering feedback from teachers fosters a collaborative approach to research, as it acknowledges their expertise and empowers them to contribute to the development of educational practices. Moreover, teachers’ questionnaires help researchers understand the effectiveness of instructional strategies, curriculum design, and classroom management techniques, enabling them to make informed decisions about educational interventions. Ultimately, integrating teachers’ voices into research processes enhances the relevance and applicability of findings, leading to the improvement of teaching practices and student outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Drawing upon the findings of this study, several recommendations can be formulated to guide language teachers in effectively leveraging multimedia programs to facilitate vocabulary acquisition in their classrooms. First and foremost, it is imperative for language teachers to recognize the potential of multimedia tools as powerful aids in vocabulary instruction. Multimedia programs offer dynamic and interactive learning experiences that can engage students and stimulate their interest in acquiring new vocabulary. As such, teachers should embrace the use of multimedia resources as integral components of their vocabulary teaching repertoire. By incorporating a variety of multimedia materials that cater to different learning styles and preferences,

educators can create inclusive learning environments where all students have the opportunity to thrive. Furthermore, the selection of appropriate multimedia materials is crucial to the success of vocabulary instruction. Teachers should carefully curate or develop multimedia resources that align with the learning objectives and language proficiency levels of their students. Authentic materials such as videos, podcasts, and news articles provide valuable opportunities for students to learn vocabulary in meaningful contexts, enhancing retention and comprehension.

Additionally, interactive games and exercises can offer engaging and enjoyable ways for students to practice and reinforce their vocabulary skills. By choosing multimedia materials thoughtfully and purposefully, teachers can maximize the effectiveness of their vocabulary instruction and create enriching learning experiences for their students. Incorporating real-life contexts and authentic materials into mobile apps is another key recommendation for language teachers. Research suggests that presenting vocabulary in authentic contexts helps students develop a deeper understanding of word meanings and usage patterns. Therefore, teachers should seek out multimedia resources that expose students to language as it is used in real-world situations, such as conversations, interviews, and cultural artifacts. By immersing students in authentic linguistic environments, teachers can foster not only vocabulary acquisition but also cultural awareness and communicative competence^[9, 14]. Moreover, fostering student interaction and collaboration with multimedia resources is essential for promoting active engagement and deeper learning. Language learning is a social and communicative process, and multimedia tools can facilitate collaborative activities that encourage students to interact with each other and with the language in meaningful ways. For example, teachers can design group projects or discussions that require students to use multimedia resources to research, analyze, and present vocabulary related to specific topics or themes. By working together in a collaborative learning environment, students can share their insights, exchange ideas, and support each other's language development.

Additionally, providing ample opportunities for student-centered exploration and discovery with multimedia resources is essential for promoting autonomous learning and self-efficacy. Teachers should empower students to take ownership of their learning by allowing them to explore and interact with multimedia materials at their own pace and according to their individual interests and preferences. For instance, teachers can create multimedia-based learning stations or online repositories where students can access a variety of resources to support their vocabulary acquisition outside the classroom. By encouraging independent exploration and self-directed learning, teachers can cultivate students' motivation and confidence in their ability to learn and use new vocabulary effectively. Furthermore, implementing formative assessment and feedback mechanisms is critical for monitoring students' progress and adjusting instruction as needed. Teachers should design tasks and activities that allow them to assess students' vocabulary knowledge and skills in authentic contexts using multimedia resources. Additionally, providing timely and constructive feedback on students' performance can help guide their learning and address any misconceptions or difficulties they may encounter. By regularly assessing student progress and providing targeted feedback, teachers can ensure that their vocabulary instruction remains responsive to the evolving needs and abilities of their students.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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2025. №10

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.